

Enabling Vertical Services with a Cross-Domain 6G Architecture and Trial Framework: The AMAZING-6G Approach

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Abstract—Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G networks promise advanced performance and flexibility for emerging vertical applications, but the full adoption of advanced technologies and features and their real-world validation remains limited. This paper focuses on the AMAZING-6G architecture for a large-scale trial framework, which aims to empower vertical industries through an integrated compute and networking continuum. This platform delivers key capabilities such as Compute-as-a-Service, Network Slicing-as-a-Service, AI-as-a-Service, and energy-efficient IoT support to improve performance and energy-efficiency of various vertical industries, stretching over healthcare, public safety, transport, and energy domains. The paper introduces the system architecture and highlights four representative use cases and their adoption of B5G/6G architectural components.

Keywords—B5G, 6G, trials, real-life validation, verticals, healthcare, transport, energy, public safety

Fig. 1: High-level view on the AMAZING-6G system and the trial framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

Large-scale trials and pilots are essential for the adoption of advanced vertical applications in the 6G era, as they enable validation and demonstration of 6G technologies under realistic operating conditions. The AMAZING-6G project aims to empower verticals with advanced networking capabilities, such as Compute-as-a-Service (CaaS), Network Slicing-as-a-Service (NSaaS), AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS), and energy-efficient Internet-of-Things (IoT) support using Reduced Capability (RedCap). In particular, the project provides verticals with an end-to-end compute and networking continuum, enabling full customization of network and compute resources and energy-efficient service operations. Recent work [1] shows that while in Europe, 5G Standalone and some dynamic slicing features are increasingly adopted in Beyond 5G (B5G)/6G trials, key capabilities such as network exposure and analytics remain largely missing, limiting full vertical integration and the realization of advanced QoS-driven services. To tackle this issue, AMAZING-6G advances 6G research by jointly integrating and validating various advanced technological enablers, such as network automation based on Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM), dynamic network slicing, automatic *gNodeB* configuration, Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) integration, edge-cloud continuum orchestration, CAMARA Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs), AI/Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) pipelines, and RedCap, within end-to-end, real-world vertical applications stretching across the healthcare, public safety, transport, and energy domains.

II. AMAZING-6G TRIAL FRAMEWORK

A. System architecture

The AMAZING-6G *logical* architecture [2], shown in Fig. 1, consists of Functional Groups (FGs) and Functional Components (FCs). FGs are grouping B5G/6G functionalities, i.e., FCs into the following four technological domains: i) Decision Making FG (taking XaaS-related intent-based decisions), ii) Communication & Network enablers FG (supporting NSaaS), iii) Compute enablers FG (supporting CaaS), and iv) Vertical enablers FG (supporting AIaaS and IoT). The vertical columns in Fig. 1 are the transversal FGs, which apply to more than one domain (e.g., End-to-end Security). The FGs of the AMAZING-6G architecture and the trial framework serve as a blueprint for implementing the B5G/6G system and its technological components in various trial sites hosting diverse vertical services. Using this framework, verticals can build complex IoT or AI-powered applications that are energy-efficient, enabled by RedCap, and energy-aware service orchestration. Also, verticals can rely on our set of Networking and Compute features and capabilities to execute their services according to their Quality of Service (QoS) and compute requirements.

To access the functionalities offered by the AMAZING-6G framework, verticals can use: i) dedicated exposure functions, such as Network Exposure Function (NEF) and Compute Exposure Function (CEF) (e.g., verticals know precisely which compute nodes are needed for the execution of their services),

and ii) intent-based network management (need more context and help from the network itself). The latter enables verticals to use the decision-making component to automatically select relevant compute nodes and perform optimal service placement (CaaS). For network slice provisioning (NSaaS), the corresponding FCs devise the network slice characteristics based on the QoS requirements expressed by verticals and take care of provisioning at the network provider side.

B. Use cases

The AMAZING-6G project covers four vertical domains: healthcare, public safety, energy, and transport. One of the Use Cases (UCs) within the *healthcare* vertical targets patch-based cardiac ultrasound assessment for diagnosis, intervention, and patient follow-up. It combines a 6G-enabled ultrasound patch with edge-based AI image analysis. Trials include: i) daily short (one-minute) ultrasound recordings for remote monitoring, requiring high-bandwidth upload (86Mbps) with minimal energy consumption, and ii) continuous monitoring using a mains-powered patch with real-time edge AI analysis, requiring high bandwidth, ultra-high availability (99.9999%), and end-to-end latency below 500 ms. In AMAZING-6G, this use case leverages energy-efficient connectivity based on 5G New Radio (5G-NR) RedCap. The goal is to assess whether stringent throughput and energy constraints can be met, while future work will focus on reducing data rates without compromising clinical accuracy, and further optimizing energy efficiency through advanced radio, edge computing (CaaS), and network slicing (NSaaS).

In the domain of *public safety*, the AR/VR-assisted Control Centres use case supports emergency operations through multi-network convergence enabled by compute and communication functionalities that ensure reliable connectivity in disrupted scenarios. These include automated backhaul deployment, gNodeB configuration, and rapid Kubernetes-based service provisioning. Designed for large-scale emergencies (e.g., wildfires or earthquakes), the system enables high-priority PPDR services via end-to-end network slicing across private and public RANs, on-demand resource orchestration, MEC support, and interconnection of B5G/6G cores. It also features AI-driven situation monitoring, autonomous control of unmanned vehicles, and XR-enhanced awareness. The AMAZING-6G trial framework offers fast service provisioning ($< 1min$), ultra-low latency ($< 20ms$), and closed-loop automation, with future extensions toward intent-based slice provisioning for faster emergency response.

One of the *energy* UCs targets joint optimization of energy consumption and user comfort in smart buildings and Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) using B5G/6G, edge-cloud computing, and distributed AI. It enables intelligent energy prosumers via AI-driven control of indoor conditions, appliance usage, and energy flows. Two scenarios are considered: i) single-building optimization with real-time monitoring and strict requirements ($> 99.999\%$ reliability, $< 20ms$ latency for control), and ii) multi-building coordination via federated learning. The solution relies on massive IoT support, low-latency and reliable connectivity, and network slicing for differentiated QoS, while edge processing ensures fast, privacy-preserving decisions, ultimately supporting scalable, human-centric, and energy-efficient building management.

One of the *transport* UCs supports Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), such as visually impaired individuals, by enabling safer urban navigation via edge-based digital twins, and B5G/6G connectivity. The UC focuses on dynamic deployment of services across edge and far-edge, i.e., Roadside Units (RSUs), depending on the network, compute, and energy conditions, with ultra-low-latency data exchange enabled via network slicing and CaaS. The system requires < 30 ms end-to-end latency and ensures QoS, resilience, and scalability under increasing load. The sensor data from RSUs, vehicles, and pedestrians is fed into an edge-hosted digital twin that assesses risk for VRUs in real time, sending alerts via a smartphone app (e.g., vibration or sound) to enhance user safety, particularly in critical scenarios like road crossing.

III. FUTURE OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSIONS

To support advanced vertical applications, 6G systems must provide a dynamically orchestrated communication compute continuum. The diversity and stringency of vertical requirements require joint optimization of latency, reliability, and energy efficiency through dynamic network slicing and intelligent service orchestration. However, the traditional static slicing approaches are insufficient in highly dynamic environments, which the AMAZING-6G platform tackles by adopting flexible NSaaS and CaaS paradigms. The investigated use cases, stretching over the healthcare, public safety, energy, and transport domains, demonstrate that many vertical applications require the simultaneous fulfillment of low latency, high throughput, high reliability, and low energy consumption, which remains a key technological challenge for 6G. In healthcare and transport scenarios, the platform enables energy-efficient communication and edge-based AI processing while preserving service accuracy and reliability. In PPDR deployments, high-priority network slices support autonomous monitoring, robotic collaboration, and XR-assisted situational awareness, highlighting the importance of real-time orchestration and low-latency interconnection. Similarly, energy use cases illustrate how AI-native automation, federated learning, and edge-cloud continuum orchestration can enable scalable, privacy-preserving, and human-centric energy management. This paper presented the AMAZING-6G system architecture as a holistic framework integrating communication, computing, IoT, and AI enablers to support tight vertical integration in B5G/6G systems and real-life validation of their services. Future work will focus on large-scale cross-domain trials, paving the way toward autonomous, sustainable, and vertically-driven 6G ecosystems.

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